

Response of rice and wheat to zinc fertilization in alkali soils

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Large areas of alkali land in the Indo-Gangetic plains are not cultivated. At the Gudda experimental farm, CSSRI, we evaluated responses to Zn application of rice and wheat on an alkali soil with pH 10.45, EC 4.08 dS/m, 94% exchangeable sodium percentage, 3.73% CaCO₃, 20% clay, 26% silt, 54% sand, 28 t gypsum requirement/ha, and 0.44 ppm DTPA-Zn.

Zero, 10, 20, 40, 80, and 120 kg ZnSO₄/ha were applied in a randomized block design with 4 replications, and 14 t gypsum/ha was surface broadcast and mixed in the upper 8-10 cm soil. Jaya rice and HD2009 wheat were grown in

Effect of Zn on the yield and Zn uptake by rice and wheat crops in alkali soil, Karnal, India.

ZnSO ₄ added (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)						Zn uptake (g/ha)				DTPA-Zn (ppm) after		
	Rice			Wheat			Rice		Wheat		Wheat	Rice	
	1980	1981	1982	1983	1980-81	1981-82	1982-83	1980	1983	1980-81	1982-83	1982-83	1983
0	5.1	5.0	6.6	5.0	1.2	1.4	2.0	144	151	28	41	0.44	0.41
10	6.0	6.1	7.5	6.0	1.6	2.2	2.9	198	302	66	105	1.87	2.06
20	6.0	5.8	7.7	6.2	1.7	2.4	2.9	221	319	73	129	3.09	3.54
40	6.0	5.9	7.5	6.1	1.6	2.2	3.1	235	273	79	139	6.05	7.00
80	6.0	5.7	7.5	6.2	1.7	2.3	3.1	244	407	108	163	10.95	12.58
120	6.0	5.7	7.5	6.1	1.6	2.4	3.0	253	414	113	193	15.45	18.13
CD (0.05)	0.61	0.62	0.67	0.26	0.36	0.60	0.32	25	29	7	22	.66	.89

sequence. ZnSO₄ and 75 kg N/ha as urea were applied basally and the remaining 75 kg N/ha was topdressed in 2 equal splits 3 and 6 wk after planting.

Rice plants in the Zn control plots were stunted and had visible Zn deficiency symptoms. Grain yield and Zn uptake by rice and wheat crops were significantly

less in the control than in Zn-treated plots.

Applying 10 kg ZnSO₄/ha significantly increased available Zn and grain yield of both crops (see table). Applying 20 to 120 kg ZnSO₄/ha did not increase yield over that with 10 kg ZnSO₄.

Responses of rice to some trace elements

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We evaluated the effect of trace elements Zn, Cu, Fe, and Mn on yield at the Government Seed Farm Rakh Mangan, D. I. Khan, Northwest Frontier Province, Pakistan. Treatments were no fertilizer (control), NPK, NPKZn, NPKCu, NPKFe, NPKMn, NPKZnCu, and NPKFeMn. Zn, Cu, Fe, and Mn were applied at 5.0, 5.0, 2.5, and 2.5 kg/ha. NPK at 120, 40, and 50 kg/ha was applied as urea, single superphosphate, and potassium sulfate. Experiments were on two clay soils. One had pH 8.0, 11% CaCO₃, 0.79% organic matter, and 3 ppm Olsen's available P. The other had pH 8.2, 13% CaCO₃, 0.81% organic matter, and 3 ppm Olsen's available P.

With Cu and Fe application, yield increased more than 10% over NPK alone. There was some yield response to Zn and Mn, but the increase was not statistically significant (see table). Our preliminary studies show the soils are Cu and Fe deficient either in absolute quantity or in availability to rice.

Effect of trace elements on rice yield, Peshawar, Pakistan.

Treatment	Trace ^a element	Paddy yield ^b (t/ha)		Increase (%) over NPK
		1982	1983	
0-0-0	O	5.3 c	5.1 f	—
120-40-50	O	7.4 c	6.5 e	—
120-40-50	Zn	7.7 ab	6.6 de	3.2
120-40-50	Cu	8.7 ab	6.9 cde	12.0
120-40-50	Fe	7.8 ab	7.7 ab	12.0
120-40-50	Mn	7.8 ab	6.8 cde	5.8
120-40-50	Zn+Cu	8.8 a	7.2 bc	15.4
120-40-50	Fe+Mn	8.0 ab	8.0 a	15.4
120-40-50	Zn+Cu+Fe+Mn	—	7.1 cd	—

^aZn = 5 kg/ha, Cu = 5 kg/ha, Fe = 2.5 kg/ha, Mn = 2.5 kg/ha. ^bMeans followed by similar letters do not differ significantly at 5% level.

Relative efficiency of simple and complex fertilizers for rice

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We compared the effects of simple and complex fertilizers on the yield of IRRI-6 on 2 soils at the Agricultural Research Station, Dera Ismail Khan, Northwest Frontier Province of Pakistan, in 1982 and 1983. Fertilizers were urea (46%N), urea plus single superphosphate (SSP)

(8.8% P), urea plus diammonium phosphate (DAP) (18% N and 20% P), and urea plus nitrophos (NP) (23% N and 10% P). N and P rates were 120 and 40 kg/ha. Soil was a clay loam with pH 7.9, 16.0% CaCO₃, and 6 ppm Olsen's available P in 1982. In 1983, the soil had pH 8.2, 18.5% CaCO₃, and 11.5 ppm Olsen's available P.

Applying urea plus DAP produced better yields than urea plus NP. The urea plus DAP treatment yielded highest in 1982 (see table), but yields were similar in 1983. In 1983, urea plus DAP pro-

Effect of simple and complex fertilizers on rice yield, Peshawar, Pakistan.^a

Treatment NPK (kg/ha)	Fertilizer	Grain yield (t/ha)			Straw ^b yield (t/ha)	Value cost ratio ^c	panicles ^b /m ²
		1982	1983	Mean			
0-0-0	No fertilizer	4.8 d	5.8 b	5.3 b	6.3 b	—	270 c
120-0-0	Urea	7.2 c	7.3 a	7.3 a	14.0 a	4.37	346 bc
120-40-0	Urea+ SSP	7.6 b	8.2 a	7.9 a	14.1 a	4.04	395 ab
120-40-0	Urea+ DAP	7.9 a	8.0 a	8.0 a	14.9 a	4.06	424 a
120-40-0	Urea + NP	7.1 c	7.3 a	7.2 a	12.3 a	2.58	387 ab

^aMeans followed by similar letters do not differ significantly at 5% level. ^b1983 data on a fresh weight basis. ^cValue of rice = \$10/100 kg. Cost of fertilizers: urea, \$19.00/100 kg; SSP, \$14.14/100 kg; DAP, \$17.28/100 kg; NP, \$13.85/100 kg. Value of straw is not included.

duced the highest straw yield and panicles /m². Urea plus DAP yielded the highest net return – a value cost ratio of 4.06.

DAP is a better complex fertilizer for rice than the others tested. Response to NP was poor because it contains 9% nitrate N, which is susceptible to leaching and denitrification. □

Nitrogen fertilization for short-duration rices

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Short-duration (105-110 d) rice varieties are grown Jun-Sep in the Cauvery Delta. We evaluated the response of ADT31 (1981) and ADT36 (1982) to 0, 30, 60, 90, and 120 kg N/ha. Soil at TNRRI is a clay loam with low available N and pH 7.5. Urea was applied 50% basal, 25% at tillering, and 25% at panicle initiation. P and K at 50 kg/ha were applied basally. Plant height and number of panicles/hill

Effect of different N levels on plant height and panicles/hill at flowering and grain yield of short-duration varieties, Aduthurai, India.

N (kg/ha)	ADT31			ADT36		
	Height (cm)	Panicles/hill	Grain yield (t/ha)	Height (cm)	Panicles/hill	Grain yield (t/ha)
0	75	4.0	3.4	68	4.9	3.5
30	82	4.6	4.5	74	5.4	4.1
60	87	5.3	4.7	76	5.9	4.8
90	91	5.6	5.2	78	6.2	5.1
120	93	5.9	6.1	81	6.5	5.5
CD (P0.05)	2	0.5	0.6	3	0.4	0.3

were recorded at flowering and the grain yield at 14% moisture.

Both varieties grew taller with increased N. Maximum height was at 120 kg N/ha. Number of panicles/hill did

not increase significantly between 90 and 120 kg N/ha. ADT31 yields at 90 and 120 kg N/ha were similar and ADT36 yielded significantly higher at 120 kg N/ha (see table). □

Preventing zinc deficiency in wetland rice

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Zn fertilizer application is becoming important as more land with Zn deficiency is discovered. Cheap, efficient Zn sources must be identified and application methodology improved. We studied the

Table 1. Soil characteristics in Zn application trials in Ludhiana, India.

Soil characteristic	Pot experiment	Field experiment
pH	8.6	8.8
Organic C (%)	0.39	0.37
Ec (mmho/cm)	0.20	0.13
Texture	Sandy loam	Sandy clay loam
Zn (ppm)	0.36	0.35

Table 2. Methods of Zn application and Zn content of wetland rice, Ludhiana, India.

Method	Zn content (ppm) at different plant ages				
	16 d	32 d	48 d	64 d	Grain maturity
No Zn	20	22	24	18	18
Root dip	85	46	38	34	29
Nursery application	112	35	31	28	28
Crop application	37	33	28	28	28
CD at 5%	5.6	6.5	3.9	4.7	2.7

Methods of Zn application and rice yield, Ludhiana, India.